

RehabMove 2018: DESIGNING AN APP-BASED PLATFORM TO PROMOTE ACTIVITY-BASED THERAPY ADHERENCE FOR SPINAL CORD INJURY

J. A. St John, J. A. Ekberg, M. J. Barton, J. Faichney, M. T. Todorovic

Griffith University, SOUTHPORT, GOLD COAST, Australia

PURPOSE: To design a dynamic and user-friendly smart device app to be used by service providers, clinicians and clients to promote adherence to personalised activity-based programs.

METHOD: In conjunction with neurorehabilitation specialists (*Making Strides*, Burleigh, Australia), app development enterprise (*App Factory*, Gold Coast, Australia), and Griffith University (*Spinal Injury Project*), a secure mobile app and web portal were developed for iPhone and Android platforms. The mobile app manages client data (personalised activity-based programs), and the web portal provides raw data access for practitioners, researchers and administrators. The app and associated web portal were developed using an iterative design approach with focus groups, alpha and beta testing involving four staff from *Making Strides*.

RESULTS: The Spinal Injury Project Rehabilitation (SIPR) mobile app contains a catalogue of activity-based exercises produced by neurorehabilitation specialists for clients to access and perform. Sets, repetitions, time, and/or weights and emotional status can be recorded and the client's progress displayed graphically in summary and individually for each exercise. Motivational push notifications are sent as reminders or when clients have achieved their targets. A web portal provides practitioners and researchers access to the raw data for each client in order to evaluate adherence and progress with client data maintained with high security including one-way encrypted passwords, email authentication, and PIN app login. Program can be re-evaluated and updated when necessary.

CONCLUSION: The SIPR mobile app enables rehabilitation service providers, clinicians and the researchers with a means to constantly monitor client participation and compliance with prescribed activity-based programs. Importantly, it provides early warning indications when clients are not participating to enable support professionals to intervene with clients to help maintain participation.